

Management

A STUDY ON JOB STRESS AMONG PRIVATE HOSPITALS EMPLOYEES IN THENI DISTRICT

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Abstract

Human resource management is an art of managing people at a work in such manner that they give their best to their organization. In simple word HRM refers to the quantitative aspects of employees working in an organization. Stress is a part of day-to-day living of every individual. We generally believe that the stress is caused by the external events and the dynamics of the environment. But we need to emphasis the fact that the Stress is caused by our reaction to the external environment.

Keywords: Human Resource Management; Stress; Attributes and Causes of Stress and Problems.

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1. Introduction

Human resource management is an art of managing people at a work in such manner that they give their best to their organization. In simple word HRM refers to the quantitative aspects of employees working in an organization.

Organizations are not mere bricks, mortar, machineries or inventories. They are people, who staff manage and organizations. HRM involves the applications of management functions and principles. The functions and principles are applied to acquisitioning, developing, maintain and remunerating employees in an organization.

Stress is a part of day-to-day living of every individual. We generally believe that the stress is caused by the external events and the dynamics of the environment. But we need to emphasis the fact that the Stress is caused by our reaction to the external environment. The manner in which we perceive and understand the changes or the particular event creates same event can bring happiness and cause. Hans Selye was one of the founding fathers of stress research. His view in

1956 was that "stress is not necessarily something bad – it all depends on how you take it. The stress of exhilarating, creative successful work is beneficial, while that of failure, humiliation or infection is detrimental." Selye believed that the biochemical effects of stress would be experienced irrespective of whether the situation was positive or negative.

2. Sources of Stress

The Environment: The natural stressors, for example, climate, commotion, swarming, contamination, movement, perilous and substandard lodging, and wrongdoing.

Social Stressors: Social stressors, for example, due dates, monetary issues, prospective employee meetings, presentations, differences, requests for your time and consideration, loss of a friend or family member, separation, and co-child rearing. These stressors emerging because of requests of the diverse social parts, for example, guardian, life partner, parental figure, and worker.

Physiological: Physiological stressors incorporate fast development of puberty, menopause, disease, maturing, conceiving an offspring, mishaps, absence of activity, poor sustenance, and rest aggravations.

Contemplations: Human cerebrum translates and sees circumstances as upsetting, troublesome, difficult or wonderful, in such circumstance our mind figures out if they are issues to us or not.

3. Review of Literature

Employee turnover is an employee's voluntary withdrawal from the organization.¹ High turnover has been a major issue in health-care organizations. Turnover of skilled staff can incur substantial costs (e.g. costs associated with recruiting and training new staff) for organizations. High staff turnover can also impact negatively on an organization's capacity to meet patient needs and provide quality care.² Turnover intention is a determinant of actual turnover behaviour. Turnover intention and turnover decisions may be an indicator of low, and decreased QWL.³

Some studies found a positive relationship between employees' QWL and their job satisfaction⁴ and organizational commitment. ⁵ Low employees' job satisfaction is a significant predictor of their turnover intention and actual turnover.⁶ Other empirical studies confirm the important role of organizational commitment in the turnover process.⁷

On the other hand, a strong inverse relationship was found between employees' job stress and their job satisfaction.⁸ Job stress also may lead to increased burnout.⁹ In addition, some studies found a relationship between employees' job stress and their organizational commitment¹⁰ and intentions to leave their workplaces.¹¹

Darshan et al (2009)¹² in their article, A study on professional stress, depression and alcohol use among Indian software professionals, observed that the software employees are professionally stressed and are at 10 times higher risk for developing depression and also significantly increase the incidence of psychiatric disorders. Preventive strategies like training in stress management, frequent screening to identify professional stress and depression at the initial stages and

addressing these issues adequately might help the software professionals cope with their profession better without affecting their lifestyle and health.

Saurabh Shrivastava and Prateek Bobhate (2010)¹³ in their study, Computer related health problems among software professionals in Mumbai: A cross-sectional study, investigated that Ocular discomfort, musculo-skeletal disorders and psycho-social problems form key category of health problems found among constant computer users. This study has also brought into focus factors contributing to the occurrence of these problems. Thus, the problem requires a multidisciplinary action and hence there is an immediate need for the concerned authorities to collaborate and enforce suitable preventive measures.

Jakkula Rao and Chandraiah (2011)¹⁴ in their article, Occupational stress, mental health and coping among information technology professionals, found that job satisfaction and mental health are correlated but not significant. However, job satisfaction was positively and significantly correlated with coping behaviour. The mental health is negatively and significantly correlated with occupational stress. It can be explained that as job satisfaction and mental health increases coping behavior increases. And as stress increases mental health decreases.

Kesavachandran et al (2012)¹⁵ in their study, Working conditions and health among employees at information technology - enabled services: A review of current evidence, identified that musculo-skeletal disorders, ocular disorders and psycho-social problems were some of the key health problems observed among software professionals. There is a need for implementation of the programs that include the concepts of ergonomics, health education, training of personnel to prevent and overcome the morbidity, as well as psycho-social problems among workers in software industry.

4. Objectives of the Study

- 1) To analyze the level occupational stress among the private hospital employees in Theni District
- 2) To examine the causes of stress in the study area
- 3) To study the methods and techniques applied for stress of the hospitals employees.
- 4) To offer suggestions based on the findings.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretations

The study depends up on the primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected by conducting a sample survey o employees working in Theni district. There are 100 staff members of private hospitals employees have been randomly selected for the present study. Stratified random sampling technique has been used for this study. A well-conceived questionnaire was used for the collection primary data. The secondary data was collected from research publications, standard journals and periodicals, books, websites, etc., this paper is also analysis of data collection by representing it in tabular form along with interpretations. The information collected and analysed for arriving at proper conclusion of the study.

Table 1: Sample size the respondents

S.No.	Designation	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Doctors	15	15
2	Nurses	25	25
3	Supervisors	15	15
4	Lab Technicians	10	10
6	Receptionists	10	10
7	Compounders	10	10
8	Room boys / servants	15	15
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

From the table 1 shows that the majority of the respondents working in stressed. Among the total respondents 25% of them come from Nurses, 15% each of them doctors, supervisors and room boys or servants. It is clearly show the above table.

Table 2: Causes of stress

S.No.		No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Role conflict	13	13
2	Role ambiguity	04	04
3	Excess of work load	25	25
4	Feeling of inequality	06	06
5	Lack of supervisory support	12	12
6	Constraints of changes rules and regulations	02	02
7	Stress due to technological problems	20	20
8	Inadequacy of role	04	04
9	Lack of group authority cohesiveness	02	02
10	Job requirements capability mismatch	12	12
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 2 indicates that major causes of stress among the employees are excess of work load (25%) and stress due to technological problems (20%). Hence it was found that employees felt that taking severe work pressure, as they were expected to handle multiple roles and responsibilities the employees suffer from stress because of lack of support from the management and colleagues.

Table 3: Various attributes of stress

SNo.	Attributes	No. of respondents	%
1	Inadequate time to finish work	20	20
2	No ability and skills	04	04
3	Hard work and skill are not approved	02	02
4	Poor infrastructure facilities	06	06
5	Unhealthy environment	06	06
6	Communication gap	18	18

7	Work life imbalance	40	40
8	Economic status	04	04
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 depicted that the various attributes relates to stress, work life imbalance is one of the major attributes which contributes to stress from employee and followed by inadequate time to finish work. This can be regarded as a factor building of stress because a lot of employee complained that they were unable to balance both the personal and professional fronts successfully. Extra more pressures and demands from work environment at times led to neglect of personal front.

Table 4: Stress level of private hospitals employees

SNo.	Attributes	No. of respondents	%
1	Good environment	18	18
2	Recognition	23	23
3	Continuous job training	10	10
4	Effective communication	11	11
5	Programme on stress management	12	12
6	Meditation	26	26
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4 reveals that the meditation from an integral part of the science of yoga has a direct positive impact on the mind giving it strength and power to resist stress. Moreover, around (23%) of the respondents as a acknowledging people's value is especially important in times of stress the above analysis the initiatives taken by the banks to reduce stress are by providing good environment continuous job training proper commutate and conducting effective stress management programmes.

Table 5: Analysis of psychological problems

SNo.	Psychological problems	No. of respondents	%
1	Anxiety	24	24
2	Tension	22	22
3	Sleeplessness	16	16
4	Boredom	10	10
5	Frustration	12	12
6	Depression	06	06
7	Fear	04	04
8	Forget fullness	06	06
	Total	100	100

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents psychologically affects stress on anxiety and tension (24% & 22%). 4% of them affected fear, but in the case of 6% of the respondents affected due to forget fullness in the study area.

6. Findings of the Study

- The majority of the respondents working in stressed. Among the total respondents 25% of them come from Nurses, 15% each of them doctors, supervisors and room boys or servants. It is clearly show the above table.
- Major causes of stress among the employees are excess of work load(25%) and stress due to technological problems(20%). Hence it was found that employees felt that taking severe work pressure, as they were expected to handle multiple roles and responsibilities the employees suffer from stress because of lack of support from the management and colleagues.
- The various attributes relates to stress, work life imbalance is one of the major attributes which contributes to stress from employee and followed by inadequate time to finish work. This can be regarded as a factor building of stress because a lot of employee complained that they were unable to balance both the personal and professional fronts successfully. Extra more pressures and demands from work environment at times led to neglect of personal front.
- The meditation from an integral part of the science of yoga has a direct positive impact on the mind giving it strength and power to resist stress. Moreover, around (23%) of the respondents as a acknowledging people's value is especially important in times of stress the above analysis the initiatives taken by the banks to reduce stress are by providing good environment continuous job training proper commutate and conducting effective stress management programmes
- A great majority of the respondents psychologically affects stress on anxiety and tension (24% & 22%). 4% of them affected fear, but in the case of 6% of the respondents affected due to forget fullness in the study area.

7. Suggestions

- Work should be properly delegated to the employees to avoid overload of work which could cause stress. Many tasks can be delegated to subordinates without losing effectiveness so that overload of work can be reduced
- Good relationship should be maintained within the employees to make the working environment healthy.
- Proper grievance handling system should be practiced to help the employees to overcome their problems.
- Employees should be motivated by giving rewards for their excellent performances. The motivation program conducted by the organization will assist the employees to perform well.
- Meditation, yoga, exercises on a daily routine basis will keep the mind and body fresh.

8. Conclusion

Stress is a slow and insidious malady which is an unavoidable one and a common problem in the workplace. The level of stress and its amount of consequences vary within and between hospitals based on the nature and type of work practices. Hospitals must begin to manage people at work differently, treating them with respect and valuing their contribution. Recognition, participation

and continuous training of employees are required to retain the skilled employees. It is the responsibility of the private hospital's organization to see that its employees undergo stress relaxation practices to overcome hospitals employees' stress which maintains the sound health of the employees.

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